

***Bz*-tetrahydroquinazolines.**

By PRAFULLA CHANDRA MITTER AND ASHUTOSH BHATTACHARYA.

Although pyrimidine and quinazoline derivatives have been known for a long time and their properties thoroughly studied, very few of their reduction products are known. Pinner ("Die Imidoether," p. 292), in the course of his investigation on the reactivity of the β -ketoic esters with amidines, found that a tetrahydroquinazoline derivative is obtained by the action of amidine hydrochloride on succino-succinic ester according to the following scheme:—

Now as succino-succinic ester has two β -diketonic groupings in the skeleton, one molecule of succino-succinic ester may react with two molecules of amidine unless carbon dioxide splits off as in (I).

It was actually found by Pinner that when aliphatic amidines were used, the former reaction (*i.e.*, splitting off of CO_2 and the condensation with amidines afterwards) preponderated; but in the

case of aromatic amidines both the reactions took place and he had to experience considerable difficulty in isolating the pure product. It was also found by him that the product

so formed in the case of aliphatic amidines is readily oxidized by the oxygen of the air in alkaline solution to a dihydroxy-quinazoline (II).

The compounds obtained by Pinner are the only known instances of quinazoline derivatives in which the benzene ring is reduced. Attempts have been made by different workers to reduce the quinazoline derivatives but in no case complete reduction was found to have taken place; only the pyrimidine ring was reduced leaving the benzene ring intact (*Ber.*, 1892, 25, 3030). It is quite obvious, therefore, that in order to obtain *bs*-tetrahydroquinazolines, we have to start with β -diketones and β -ketonic esters with a reduced benzene ring and the substances most suitable for this purpose were found to be acetyl *cyclohexanone* and ethyl *cyclohexan-1-one- β -carboxylate* and their derivatives. *Bz*-tetrahydro-quinazolines are likely to give octahydroquinazolines on reduction but our attempts in this direction have so far not been attended with complete success. We have tried the action of benzamidine, *p*-toluamidine and guanidine on β -diketones and β -ketonic esters and attempt has also been made to prepare an octahydro-derivative by reducing a tetrahydro-derivative with sodium and alcohol.

The β -diketones and β -ketonic esters employed are the acetyl *cyclohexanone* and its homologues and ethyl *cyclohexan-1-one- β -carboxylate* and its homologues. Hydroxymethylene *cyclohexanone* has also been used in one case.

In his pyrimidine synthesis, Pinner used potassium carbonate as the condensing agent; we also used the same reagent at first but the product obtained was of such an unstable nature that, on attempting to crystallise from alcohol, it decomposed into its

constituent components. Sodium ethoxide was then substituted for potassium carbonate solution. Tetrahydroquinazolines were obtained but the yield was poor—being only 33 per cent. of the acetyl *cyclohexanone* used. To increase the yield, piperidine was subsequently used under similar conditions and the yield increased from 33 to 47 per cent. This use of piperidine as the condensing reagent was applied only in the case of β -diketones; but in the case of β -ketonic esters, sodium ethoxide was quite satisfactory, the yield being theoretical. It was also found that whereas in the case of β -diketones the whole thing required to be heated for 2 to 3 hours on the water-bath, in the case of β -ketonic esters the reaction takes place even at the ordinary temperature though not completely,—confirming thereby the view that β -ketonic esters are, in general, more reactive than the β -diketones.

EXPERIMENTAL.

2-Phenyl-4-methyl-bz-tetrahydroquinazoline.

This was prepared by the condensation of benzamidine hydrochloride with acetyl *cyclohexanone* in the presence of sodium ethoxide:

Benzamidine hydrochloride was prepared by Pinner's method from benzonitrile, and acetyl *cyclohexanone*, according to the method of Borsche (*Annalen*, 1910, 377, 70) from *cyclohexanone*.

Sodium (0.85 g.) was dissolved in a slight excess of absolute alcohol and benzamidine hydrochloride (3.35 g.) was added. Sodium chloride precipitated out and the benzamidine went into solution. Acetyl *cyclohexanone* (3 g.) was then added and the mixture heated under a reflux on the water-bath for 2 hours. Excess of alcohol was driven off and the substance precipitated out by the addition of water. The yield of the crude product was 30 to 33 per cent. of the acetyl *cyclohexanone* used. In later experiments by the use of piperidine as the condensing reagent, the yield increased from 33 to 47 per cent. of the acetyl *cyclohexanone* used; by the use of this reagent the mass becomes viscous and solidifies after 2

to 3 hours on the addition of water. It was crystallised from dilute alcohol; white light feathery crystals, m. p. 108°, were obtained. (Found: N, 12.88; C, 80.12; H, 7.44. $C_{11}H_{16}N_2$ requires N, 12.50; C, 80.85; H, 7.14 per cent.). Its *picrate* has the m. p. 144°-145°.

Condensation of Benзамidine Hydrochloride with Acetyl cyclohexanone, with Potassium Carbonate as the Condensing Agent.

Benzamidine hydrochloride (1 g.) dissolved in 3 c.c. of water, was mixed with a saturated solution of potassium carbonate. The clear solution being mixed with acetyl *cyclohexanone* (1.5 g.) immediately deposited an oily product which quickly solidified. The mixture was left overnight. The crude product melted between 106° and 109°. It was supposed that it might be an intermediate product; but in attempting to crystallise it either from alcohol or acetic acid it decomposed, setting the acetyl *cyclohexanone* free.

2-p-Tolyl-4-methyl-bz-tetrahydroquinazoline.

p-Toluamidine hydrochloride, prepared according to the method of Pinner, was condensed with acetyl *cyclohexanone*. The procedure is the same as in the case of benzamidine hydrochloride. From 3.64 g. *p*-toluamidine hydrochloride the yield of the crude product is 0.8 to 1 gm. It is crystallised from dilute alcohol: light feathery crystals, m. p. 129°-130°, are obtained. It is soluble in benzene, ether alcohol, acetone, ethyl acetate and petroleum ether. (Found: N, 12.99. $C_{14}H_{18}N_2$ requires N, 11.76 per cent.).

2-Amino-4-methyl-bz-tetrahydroquinazoline.

Finely powdered guanidine nitrate (2.7 g.) was condensed with acetyl *cyclohexanone* (3 g.) in the presence of sodium ethoxide (0.37 g. Na). The procedure is the same as in the previous cases, the heating required in this case being 7 to 8 hours; yield of the crude product is 1.5 gm. It is crystallised from ethyl acetate; m. p. 177°-178°. (Found: N, 23.07. $C_8H_{11}N_3$ requires N, 25.76 per cent.).

2-Phenyl-4:8-dimethyl-bz-tetrahydroquinazoline.

2-Methyl-6-acetyl-1-*cyclohexanone* (1.5 g.), prepared as in the case of acetyl *cyclohexanone* from *o*-methyl-*cyclohexanone*, was

condensed with benzamidine hydrochloride (1.53 g.) in the presence of sodium ethoxide (0.23 g. Na).

The procedure is the same as in the case of 2-phenyl-4-methyl-*bz*-tetrahydroquinazoline. Yield of the crude product is 0.7 gm. It is crystallised from dilute alcohol; m.p. 84°-85°. (Found: N, 11.48. $C_{15}H_{15}N_3$ requires N, 11.76 per cent.).

2-p-Tolyl-4:8-dimethyl-bz-tetrahydroquinazoline.

p-Toluamidine hydrochloride (1.6 g.) was condensed with 2-methyl-6-acetyl-1-cyclohexanone (1.5 g.) in the presence of sodium ethoxide (0.23 g. Na). The procedure is the same as before. Yield of the crude product is 0.6 gm. It is crystallised from dilute alcohol; m.p. 95°. (Found: N, 11.74. $C_{17}H_{20}N_3$ requires N, 11.11 per cent.).

2-Amino-4:8-dimethyl-bz-tetrahydroquinazoline.

2-Methyl-6-acetyl-cyclohexan-1-one (3 g.) was condensed with guanidine nitrate (2.2 g.) in the presence of sodium ethoxide (0.45 g. Na). The method of procedure is the same as in the case of 2-amino-4-methyl-*bz*-tetrahydroquinazoline. Yield of the crude product is 2 g. It is crystallised from alcohol; m.p. 103°-104°. (Found: N, 23.85. $C_{10}H_{13}N_3$ requires N, 23.72 per cent.).

2-Phenyl-4:7-dimethyl bz-tetrahydroquinazoline.

3-Methyl-6-acetylcyclohexan-1-one (3 g.), prepared in the same way as acetyl cyclohexanone from *m*-methylcyclohexanone, was condensed with benzamidine hydrochloride (3.5 g.) in the presence of sodium ethoxide (0.44 g. Na). The whole thing was heated on the water-bath, as in the previous cases, for 8 hours. In this case the smell of NH_3 was quite perceptible probably due to the decomposition of the amidine in the presence of sodium ethoxide. Yield of the crude product is 1 gm. It is crystallised from dilute alcohol; m.p. 111°-112°. (Found: N, 12.20. $C_{15}H_{15}N_3$ requires N, 11.76 per cent.).

2-p-Tolyl-4:7-dimethyl-bz-tetrahydroquinazoline.

3-Methyl-6-acetyl-cyclohexan-1-one (3 g.) was condensed with *p*-toluamidine hydrochloride (3.3 g.) in the presence of sodium

ethoxide (0.44 g. Na). Procedure is the same as in the previous cases. Yield of the crude product is 0.5 gm. It is crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 135°. (Found: N, 11.38. $C_{17}H_{20}N_2$ requires N, 11.11 per cent.).

Bs-TETRAHYDRO-HYDROXYQUINAZOLINES.

2-Phenyl-4-hydroxy-bz-tetrahydroquinazoline.

Ethyl *cyclohexan-1-one-2-carboxylate* prepared according to the method of Kötze and Hesse (*Annalen*, 1905, 342, 306) was condensed with benzamidine hydrochloride in the presence of sodium ethoxide. On adding the ester (2 g.) to the benzamidine hydrochloride (1.84 g.) in sodium ethoxide (0.26 g. Na) solution, a yellowish colouration developed with some evolution of heat, and the smell of NH_3 was quite perceptible. It was then heated on the water-bath for 2 hours. Yield of the crude product was 2.3 gm. It was crystallised from hot absolute alcohol mixed with animal charcoal. The crystals formed perfectly white, long needles, m.p. 238°. (Found: N, 12.04. $C_{14}H_{14}N_2O$ requires N, 12.30 per cent.).

2-p-Tolyl-4-hydroxy-bz-tetrahydroquinazoline.

Ethyl *cyclohexan-1-one-2-carboxylate* (3 g.) was condensed with *p*-toluamididine hydrochloride (3 g.) in the presence of sodium ethoxide (0.4 g. Na).

The condensation was effected as in the previous case, the yield being 4 g. (almost quantitative). It was crystallised from hot alcohol mixed with animal charcoal in colourless needles, m.p. 255°—257°. (Found: N, 11.93. $C_{15}H_{16}N_2O$ requires N, 11.66 per cent.).

2-Amino-4-hydroxy-bz-tetrahydroquinazoline.

Ethyl *cyclohexan-1-one-2-carboxylate* (3 g.) was condensed with guanidine nitrate (2.25 g.) in the presence of sodium ethoxide (0.4 g. Na). The experiment was effected as in the previous cases but though there was a rise of temperature there was no change of colour in this case. Yield of the crude product was 3.2 gm. It is insoluble in all the common solvents. For purification, this

substance was dissolved in acetic acid, filtered and the base reprecipitated by means of ammonium Hydroxide. The precipitate was then thoroughly washed with water. It did not melt even above 300°. (Found: N, 25.42. $C_9H_{11}N_2O$ requires N, 25.45 per cent.).

2-Phenyl-4-hydroxy-8-methyl-bz-tetrahydroquinazoline.

Ethyl 2-methyl-cyclohexan-1-one-6-carboxylate, prepared from *o*-methylcyclohexanone in the same way as ethyl cyclohexan-1-one-2-carboxylate, was condensed with benzamidine hydrochloride in the presence of sodium ethoxide. On the addition of ethyl 2-methyl-cyclohexan-1-one-6-carboxylate to the mixture of benzamidine hydrochloride and sodium ethoxide, a yellow colour developed. It was kept overnight and on experimenting with a part of it the next day, it was found that the reaction product did not go into solution although the reacting substances are all soluble in water. This shows that the reaction takes place even at the ordinary temperature though not completely. It was then heated on the water-bath for 2 hours. It is fairly soluble in hot alcohol, benzene and ethyl acetate. It crystallised from dilute alcohol, in tiny white needles, m.p. 200°. (Found: N, 12.0. $C_{15}H_{18}N_2O$ requires N, 11.66 per cent.).

2-p-Tolyl-4-hydroxy-8-methyl-bz-tetrahydroquinazoline.

The condensation was effected between ethyl 2-methyl-cyclohexan-1-one-6-carboxylate (2 g.) with *p*-toluamidine hydrochloride (1.7 g.) using sodium ethoxide (0.25 g. Na) as the condensing reagent. The experimental details are the same as in the previous experiment. It was crystallised from absolute alcohol mixed with some animal charcoal. Needle-shaped crystals, m.p. 281°-183°, were obtained. (Found: N, 11.45. $C_{16}H_{18}N_2O$ requires N, 11.02 per cent.).

2-Amino-4-hydroxy-8-methyl-bz-tetrahydroquinazoline.

The condensation was effected as in the previous cases between ethyl 2-methylcyclohexan-1-one-6-carboxylate (2 g.) and guanidine nitrate (1.32 g.) in the presence of sodium ethoxide (0.25 g. Na). Yield of the crude product was 1.2 gm. It was crystallised from alcohol in very fine perfectly white needles, which do not melt even

at 300° (Found: N, 28.66. $C_9H_{11}ON_2$ requires N, 28.46 per cent.).

2-Phenyl-4-hydroxy-7-methyl-bz-tetrahydroquinazoline.

Ethyl 3-methyl-cyclohexan-1-one-6-carboxylate (2 g.) prepared from *m*-methylcyclohexanone according to the method of Kotz and Hesse (*loc. cit.*), was condensed with benzamidine hydrochloride (1.7 g.) in the presence of sodium ethoxide (0.25 g. Na) as in the previous experiments. Yield of the crude product was 1.8 gm. The condensation product was at first crystallised from dilute alcohol and then from benzene mixed with animal charcoal. Needles of bluish tinge, m.p. 214°—216, are obtained; these are sparingly soluble in ligroin with which they were washed to get rid of the last traces of impurities. (Found: N, 12.23. $C_{15}H_{19}ON_2$ requires N, 11.66 per cent.).

2-p-Tolyl-4-hydroxy-7-methyl-bz-tetrahydroquinazoline.

The condensation was effected between ethyl 3-methylcyclohexan-1-one-6-carboxylate (2 g.) and *p*-toluamidine hydrochloride (1.7 g.) using sodium ethoxide (0.25 g. Na) as the condensing agent, as in the previous experiments. Yield of the crude product was 2.5 gm. The substance was crystallised from benzene; m.p. 254°—256°. (Found: N, 11.09. $C_{16}H_{21}ON_2$ requires N, 11.02 per cent.).

2-Amino-4-hydroxy-7-methyl-bz-tetrahydroquinazoline.

The substance was prepared by condensing 3-methyl-cyclohexan-1-one-6-carboxylate (2 g.) with guanidine nitrate (1.32 g.) in the presence of sodium ethoxide (0.25 g. Na). Yield of the crude product was 2.2 g. It was crystallised from a large excess of hot water. The crystals are perfectly white needles, fibrous in nature. They do not melt above 300° but there is only a slight charring near about 310°. (Found: N, 23.83. $C_9H_{13}ON_2$ requires N, 23.46 per cent.).

2-Phenyl-bz-tetrahydroquinazoline.

Hydroxymethylene cyclohexanone prepared by the method of Wallach (*Annalen*, 1903, 329, 109) was condensed with benzamidine

hydrochloride using piperidine as the condensing reagent. Benza-
midine hydrochloride (8.7 g.) was dissolved in alcohol, 1 c.c. of
piperidine was added and subsequently the required quantity of
hydroxymethylene cyclohexanone (3 g.) introduced. It was then
heated on the water-bath for six hours, when the solution became red.
Excess of alcohol was driven off and the product was precipitated
out by means of water. Yield of the crude product was 2.4 gm. As
the substance has a low m.p., it was thrice slowly crystallised from
absolute alcohol at ordinary temperature; m.p. 52°–53°. (Found:
N, 13.52. $C_{14}H_{14}N_2$, requires N, 13.38 per cent.).

The condensation between hydroxymethylene cyclohexanone and
p-toluamidine hydrochloride and guanidine nitrate will be described in
a later paper.

Reduction of 2-Phenyl-4-methyl-bz-tetrahydroquinazoline.

The substance (2 g.) was reduced with absolute alcohol (170 c.c.)
and sodium (18.4 g.) under reflux condenser. After all the sodium
had dissolved in alcohol, excess of alcohol was driven off and water
added to dissolve sodium ethoxide when an oil floated on the surface
of the water. There was also much tarry matter produced. The
oil was extracted with ether, dried over sodium sulphate, and dis-
tilled in *vacuo*. Copious white fumes came out and only 4 or 5 drops
of a heavy yellow oil could be collected. It had a very bad smell
like that of a fish oil. It did not solidify even when it was kept in a
desiccator for 7 days. A *picrate* of the substance was then prepared.
The *picrate* melts at 240° whereas the *picrate* obtained from 2-phenyl-
4-methyl-bz-tetrahydroquinazoline melts at 144°–145°. The
quantity of *picrate* being very small, the original substance could not
be regenerated. This will be investigated in a subsequent paper.

